

A STUDY ON COMPETENCY MAPPING TOWARDS FACULTY IN PRIVATE ARTS & SCIENCE COLLEGES IN DINDIGUL TOWN, TAMIL NADU

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ABSTRACT

The success of a nation depends on the competency and skill that its younger generation possess. This depends on the educational qualification of the individual, which is largely dependent on the faculty which the student encounters during his/her graduation. Keeping this as an objective, this research tries to identify the required competencies to be possessed by a faculty. The study is about competency mapping among faculty in arts and science colleges in Dindigul town, Tamil Nadu. Ample analysis has been conducted and proper suggestions and recommendations have been provided.

KEYWORDS: Competency, strategy, learning skill, communication skills, subject knowledge, identification of student's needs

INTRODUCTION

Competency mapping, the buzz word in any industry is not complicated as it may appear. At the heart of any successful activity lies a competence or skill. In the recent years, various thought leaders in business strategy have emphasized the need to identify what competencies a business needs, in order to compete in a specific environment. Competency mapping is a strategic HR framework for monitoring the performance and development of human resource in organizations.

The current globalization of economy necessitates innovative approaches in managing the work force. The fast changes happening in the demography and social systems thereof have given breathing space for various HR practices enhancing the employee productivity and growth. And one of the most commonly used HR practice is competency mapping for development of the employees. Identifying and development of the competencies in organization enable better performance management as well as reward and recognition systems leading to career and succession planning programmes. Also competency mapping is a strategic HR frame work for monitoring the performance.

The success of a nation depends on the competency and skill that its younger generation possess. This competency and skill is greatly related to the educational qualifications of an individual. Institutions and its faculty play a vital role in enhancing the education of an individual. Hence, the researcher feels that this study is very essential in the current scenario.

INDIAN EDUCATION INDUSTRY

The Indian education industry is poised for growth. This sector is changing rapidly with more private players entering the field. The government is also taking many measures to improve the quality of education in India. This industry is going to achieve its peak as the idea of business via education catches up.

Fifty percent of India's population is the youth. This means that the Indian education sector is huge with a population of 1.13 billion. India has around 367 universities, 18,000 colleges, about half a million teachers, and 11 million pupils. The private education industry is estimated to be between 20,000–25,000 crores. There are about 1,500 management institutes, 3,500 engineering institutes, and 1,200 medical colleges in the country.

With an increase in the average Indian household, more money is being kept aside for education purposes. Also, because of the initiatives of the government, more students are enrolling themselves for higher education. This means that more colleges are needed to cater to these students. Also, the demand for education is inflexible; that is, no matter what, the education sector is not going to collapse.

ARTS AND SCIENCE COLLEGES IN DINDIGUL TOWN

There are near to 17 arts & science colleges in Dindigul town. On an average 80 faculty are working in each college. Hence, the population size is approximately 1360. Each arts and science college possess its own rich cultural and historical background. The courses offered are different among colleges. Hence, faculty working in a college highly differs with the faculty from other college in terms of competency and skill.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

As already stated by the researcher, the success of a nation largely depends on the competency and skill of its youth population. This solely lies in the hands of their teachers. The faculties, an individual meets during his/her graduation play a vital role in his/her career development. In this regard, the following problems have been identified.

- What are the essential competencies to be possessed by a faculty?
- What is the level of competency possessed?
- What is the standard of competency expected?
- What is the competency gap?
- What are the corrective measures for eliminating the deficiency?

OBJECTIVE

The primary objective of this research is to study competency mapping towards faculty in private arts & science colleges in Dindigul Town, Tamil Nadu. The secondary objectives of the study are

- To identify the essential competencies to be possessed by a faculty.
- To analyse the level of competency possessed.
- To determine the competency gap.
- To suggest corrective measures for eliminating the deficiency.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Harvard psychologist David McClelland (1970) first suggested the importance of testing for competence rather than intelligence. Subsequently, competency models have been used worldwide to establish the building blocks of superior performance in many professional and technical academic, organizational, and manufacturing endeavors.

Kofi Annan (UN, 1999) describes competencies as the combination of skills, attributes, and behaviors that are directly related to successful performance on the job. UN further classifies three categories of competencies for its employees: Core or generic competencies for all staff (e.g., communication, teamwork) Managerial competencies (e.g., empowering others, decision-making) Technical or specific competencies related to specific jobs (e.g., one job entails the competence to “receive, identify, register, and distribute letters, documents and/or other objects.”).

MilyVelayudhanT.K (2011) assessed the competency of the employees of two software companies relating to 20 broad categories. The dimensions taken for consideration were Drive for results, Process management, Functional expertise, Personal effectiveness & ability to influence, Innovation, Team effectiveness, Customer service, Self-development orientation, Analytical thinking, Physical ability, Knowledge, Aptitude, Motivation, Communication, Leadership, Managerial ability, Negotiations, Personal values, Social skills, Technical competence. Simple random method was used to collect the data from the respondents. Tools like t-test were used to identify the present competency levels and the competency gap. The results showed that Drive for Results(0.028), Process Management(0.028), Functional Expertise(0.031), Personal Effectiveness and ability to influence(0.036), Innovation(0.011), Customer Service(.008), Analytical Thinking(0.034), Knowledge (0.000), Attitude (0.000), Motivation(0.004), Communication(0.035), Leadership(0.034), Negotiation(0.025), Personal Values(0.001) had significance value less than 0.05. So it was inferred that the mean levels are not the same among the IT professional with different companies. Also from the results, it is clear that Null Hypotheses are not to be rejected in the following dimension: Team effectiveness, Self-Development orientation, Physical ability, Social skills, Technical Competency, since the significant value is more than 0.05. In all the dimensions where significant differences are found, the employees of CTS scored higher values compared to HCL

employees. It is found that the performance levels of CTS employees are higher when compared to the employees of HCL. The gaps are found to be high among the employees of HCL in most of the dimensions. These could be developed by giving training and personality development classes for the employees.

Based on the Conference “Competencies: Communication for Development and Social Change” Held at the Rockefeller Foundation Bellagio Study and Conference Center Bellagio, Italy January 28-February 1, 2002 - Skills that received the highest ratings include the ability to understand the target audience and the context and culture in which people live; the ability to listen and observe; and the ability to communicate clearly and effectively.

- Knowledge that received the highest ratings includes knowledge of local conditions, community issues, and cross-cultural issues.
- Attitudes that received the highest ratings included respect for human and cultural diversity and belief in the importance of participation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Descriptive research design was used to study the competency mapping among faculty in Dindigul town. The primary data was collected based on simple random sampling method. Structured Questionnaire was used to collect primary data from 100 samples from faculty in arts & science colleges in Dindigul town, Tamil Nadu, India. The secondary data was collected from the articles, newspapers, books and internet. The Reliability Analysis, Two Way ANOVA test, Mann-Whitney U test and Chi-Square Analysis were used to analyse the data collected. The collected data have been analyzed with the help of SPSS 20.0 package.

RELIABILITY ANALYSIS

H0: The instrument is not reliable

H1: The instrument is reliable

Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
.920	24

The value of Cronbach’s Alpha is .920 and the no of items (questions) is 24. Since the value of Alpha is higher than the accepted value of .70(Nunnally, 1988), we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. Hence, we say that the instrument is reliable and can be used with other statistical procedures for further investigation.

CHI-SQUARE TEST

Gender and Learning Skills

H0: There is no significant difference between Gender and Learning Skills.

H1: There is significant difference between Gender and Learning Skills.

Particulars		Learning Skills				Total
		Disagree	Mutual	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Gender	1	1	11	33	37	82
	2	4	2	4	8	18
Total		5	13	37	45	100

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	14.379	3	.002
Likelihood Ratio	10.644	3	.014

The Pearson Chi-square value of gender and learning skills is 14.379 and the corresponding significant value is .002. As the calculated significant value is less than .050, we accept the alternative hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant difference between Gender and learning Skills.

Age Group and Adaptability

H0: There is no significant difference between Age Group and Subject knowledge.

H1: There is a significant difference between Age Group and Subject knowledge.

		Subject knowledge				Total
		Disagree	Mutual	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Age group	1	0	0	1	1	2
	2	1	5	1	3	10
	3	0	16	36	21	73
	4	0	2	5	3	10
	5	0	0	2	2	4
	6	0	0	0	1	1
Total		1	23	45	31	100

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	19.777	15	.181
Likelihood Ratio	17.217	15	.306

The Pearson Chi-square value of age group and subject knowledge is 19.777 and the corresponding significant value is .181. As the calculated significant value is more than .05, we accept the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no significant difference between Age Group and Subject knowledge.

MANN-WHITNEY U TEST

H0: There is an association between Gender & Communication skills

H1: There is an association between Gender & Communication skills

	Gender	No of Respondents	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Communication skills	Male	82	54.12	4438.00
	Female	18	34.00	612.00
	Total	100		

Test Statistics	
	Communication skills
Mann-Whitney U	441.000
Wilcoxon W	612.000
Z	-2.862
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.004
a. Grouping Variable: Gender	

The Mann-Whitney U test value of gender and communication skills is 441.000 and the corresponding significant value is .004. As the calculated significant value is less than .01, we accept the alternative hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant association between Gender and Communication skills.

TWO WAY ANOVA ANALYSIS

H0: Gender & Experience does not influence identification of student's needs

H1: Gender & Experience influences identification of student's needs

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects					
Dependent Variable: Identification of student's needs					
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	9.041	9	1.005	1.551	.142
Intercept	577.765	1	577.765	892.385	.000
Gender	.019	1	.019	.029	.865
Experience	4.328	5	.866	1.337	.256
Gender * Experience	5.905	3	1.968	3.040	.033
Total	1565.000	100			

The Two way ANOVA value of gender, experience and identification of student's needs is 3.040 and the corresponding significant value is .033. As the calculated significant value is less than .05, we accept the alternative hypothesis and conclude that Gender and Experience influences identification of student's needs.

SUGGESTIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings from the analysis, the researcher has put forward the following suggestions and recommendations.

- Periodical training & development programs must be imparted to the faculty for improving their competencies.
- Training programs must be designed based on a proper conduction of needs analysis.
- Proper mentoring system should be set in place.
- Importance must be given for improving the following competency among faculties
- Learning skills
- Subject knowledge
- Communication skills
- Identification of student's needs

CONCLUSION

In this study, the researcher scanned through some of the available studies related to Competency mapping. With the help of the review the researcher is in a better position to formulate the research. The soundness of any educational institution depends upon the efficiency of the faculty employed. By implementing the suggestions provided by the

researcher, the institution may grow in the future. The value of the institution may also be increased, while implementing the researcher's suggestions. This will finally help in augmenting the competencies possessed by the youth population in our nation.

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